

SIMULATION OF CRYSTALLIZATION BEHAVIOR DURING THERMOPLASTIC TAPE PLACEMENT PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

The crystallization behavior of thermoplastic composites during tape placement process has been analyzed using a finite element method. A crystallization kinetics model was fully incorporated into the heat transfer analysis. Crystallinity levels were predicted under a number of different conditions.

INTRODUCTION

Thermoplastic composite materials during processing undergo microstructural changes, which affect their subsequent properties. These changes include melting and crystallization, development of residual strains, resin flow, degradation of the matrix, void formation, and consolidation. All of these are known to be strongly affected by temperature. Understanding these changes and being able to predict them is essential to ensuring the good quality of fabricated parts.

In the thermoplastic tape placement process, an incoming composite tape is bonded to a previously laid and consolidated laminate under heat and pressure locally applied to the interface (Figure 1). Consolidation is achieved by squeezing out the entrapped air under the pressure of a compaction shoe or roller and by allowing interlaminar molecular diffusion of polymer chains to take place. By laying additional layers in different directions, a part with desired thickness and properties can be fabricated. Filament winding is a special case of the tape placement process, in which a tape is wound on a rotating cylindrical mandrel to form the part.

Crystallinity of the matrix affects mechanical performance of the composite [1-4]. In order to control part quality, therefore, one should be able to the effects of processing parameters on the crystallization behavior of the matrix. It is then possible to tailor the processing parameters to obtain optimum properties.

Crystallization rates are usually measured under isothermal conditions using differential scanning calorimetry. It is also possible to measure crystallization rates under nonisothermal conditions in

$$k_L \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} + k_T \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} + \rho m_m H_f v_x \frac{dc_m}{dx} = \rho C_p v_x \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \quad (1)$$

where k_L and k_T are the longitudinal and transverse conductivities (W/m°C), respectively, of the composite, v_x is the velocity of the roller (m/s), ρ is the density of the composite (kg/m³) and C_p is the specific heat (J/kg°C), H_f is the heat of melting of a fully crystalline phase, and m_m is the mass fraction of the matrix.

Crystallinity levels within the laminate are calculated using the crystallization kinetics model. Since crystallization is a strong function of temperature, thermal and crystallization analyses are fully coupled.

CRYSTALLIZATION KINETICS

The model proposed by Choe and Lee [18] for nonisothermal crystallization of PEEK is adopted to describe crystallization kinetics during the tape laying process. It is based on Tobin equation for isothermal phase transformation kinetics [8-10].

$$\frac{\dot{c}_v(t)}{c_v(\infty)} = k_1 \exp\left(-\frac{3E_d}{RT}\right) \exp\left(-\frac{3\psi_1 T_m^0}{T(T_m^0 - T)}\right) t^2 \left[1 - \frac{c_v(t)}{c_v(\infty)}\right]^2 + k_2 \exp\left(-\frac{4E_d}{RT}\right) \exp\left(-\frac{(3\psi_1 + \psi_2)T_m^0}{T(T_m^0 - T)}\right) \int_0^t (t - \tau)^2 \left[1 - \frac{c_v(\tau)}{c_v(\infty)}\right] d\tau \quad (2)$$

where k_1 and k_2 are given by

$$\begin{aligned} k_1 &= 4\pi N_o G_o^3 \\ k_2 &= 4\pi I_o G_o^3 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

c_v is the volume fraction crystallinity at time t , $c_v(\infty)$ is the volume fraction crystallinity at infinite time for the given temperature. N_o is the number of heterogeneous nuclei per unit volume, which decreases with increasing melt temperature as shown in Figure 2, the exponent n is 3 for three-dimensional growth of spherulites.

Figure 2. Plot of the number of heterogeneous nuclei per unit volume, N_o (# of nuclei/ cm³), as a function of melt temperature [18].

Choe and Lee [18] determined the constants in Eqn (2) by a nonlinear regression analysis of nonisothermal data. Crystallization as described by Eqn (2) occurs only when the temperature is between the melting point (T_m) and the glass transition temperature. That is, time t in Eqn (2) elapses only in this temperature range.

Since Eqn (2) could only explain crystallization behavior of the polymer, the model proposed by Maffezzoli *et al.* [23] is used to describe crystal melting kinetics of the process.

$$c_v(t) = c_v(t_{in}) \left(1 - 0.5 \int_{t_{in}}^t K dt \right)^2 \quad (4)$$

where t_{in} is the initial time. K is described by an Arrhenius relation.

$$K = K_0 \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{RT}\right) \quad (5)$$

Equation (2) is used during cooling from melting temperature (T_m) to glass transition temperature and during heating from glass transition up to 320 °C. Equation (4) is used during heating from 320 °C and whenever temperature is above the melting temperature (345 °C). Below glass transition, crystallization rate is assumed to be zero. The transition temperature between crystallization and melting is chosen to be 320 °C, where both models predict very small rates. The initial crystallinity and time, $c_v(t_{in})$ and t_{in} in Eqn (4), are then the values resulting from Eqn (2) at 320 °C.

Equation (2) requires a value for the equilibrium crystallinity $c_v(\infty)$. The available data indicates the equilibrium crystallinity falling off with decreasing temperature (Table 1). Therefore, in this study unlike the model developed by Choe and Lee [18], the equilibrium crystallinity is assumed to be temperature dependent and is obtained from Table 1 by interpolation. When the crystallinity at a temperature exceeds the corresponding equilibrium crystallinity level, i.e., when the relative crystallinity α is greater than unity, the resulting crystallization rate is assumed to be zero. Accordingly, time t in Eqn (2) does not elapse.

Table 1. Isothermal crystallization data for PEEK [15, 20, 24, 25].

Temperature ° C	Crystallinity	
	$c_v(\infty)$	$c_m(\infty)$
320 ° C	0.375	0.40
310 ° C	0.317	0.34
295 ° C	0.279	0.30
200 ° C	0.212	0.23
164 ° C	0.165	0.18
160 ° C	0.147	0.16
158 ° C	0.0764	0.084
155 ° C	0.0628	0.069

SOLUTION OF PROCEDURE

Figure 3 shows the mesh structure, in which nonuniform rectangular elements are used. The final equation [26] is given by

$$\{T_u\} = [K_{uu}]^{-1}(\{P_u\} - [K_{us}]\{T_s\}) \quad (6)$$

where $\{T_u\}$ is the vector of unspecified node temperatures, $\{T_s\}$ is the vector of specified node temperatures. $[K_{uu}]$, $[K_{us}]$, $\{P_u\}$ are parts of the global matrix and global force vector [26].

Given the boundary conditions, material properties and heat generation, unknown node temperatures can be calculated from Eqn (6). However, density ρ , thermal conductivities k_L and k_T and specific heat C_p are functions of temperature. Consequently, $[K_{uu}]$, $[K_{us}]$, and $\{P_u\}$ will contain temperature dependent terms. Besides, the effect of heat generation through crystallization is also included in the heat transfer analysis. Calculation of the crystallization rates will then require the temperature field within the laminate, which is not known at the beginning. In order to tackle this problem, an iterative solution procedure was followed. In the first iteration, average values of the temperature dependent material properties were used and crystallization rates were not calculated. In subsequent iterations, nodal temperatures obtained in the previous iteration were used to determine temperature dependent material properties and crystallization rates.

Figure 3. Part of the mesh structure used in the analysis. Horizontal and vertical dimensions are not on scale.

In order to determine crystallization rates, temperature profiles at the center and top of each ply were calculated from the nodal temperatures by linear interpolation. Material entering the control volume experiences this temperature field within the time set by the roller velocity. Given the temperature history, crystallinity levels within each ply were calculated using Eqn (2). From this data, crystallinity gradients (dc_m/dx) at the center of each element were then found by interpolation and incorporated into the heat transfer analysis

The iterative process is continued until the maximum difference in temperature profiles obtained in two consecutive iterations becomes less than 1°C . After five or eight iterations, the maximum difference usually satisfies this requirement.

In every lay-up, crystallization levels in previously laid plies are updated unless the maximum temperature in a certain ply is below the glass transition temperature or crystallinity is less than the equilibrium crystallinity for that temperature.

RESULTS

A computer code was developed for the aforementioned solution procedure. Crystallinity levels within the laminate were obtained for different sets of process parameters.

Material properties used in the program are given in Table 2, which pertain to carbon-fiber-reinforced-Polyetheretherketone, APC-2.

Table 2. Material property data for APC-2.

ρ , density (temperature dependent)	ref. 27
first iteration value	1560 kg/m ³
initial tape crystallinity	0.0
T_m , melting temperature, (ref. 2)	345 °C

T_g , glass transition temperature, (ref. 20)	145 °C
k_L , longitudinal conductivity (temp. dependent) first iteration value	ref. 28 6.0 W/m °C
k_T , transverse conductivity (temperature dependent) first iteration value	ref. 28 0.72 W/m °C
C_p , heat capacity (temperature dependent) first iteration value	ref. 28 1425 J/kg °C
H_f , heat of melting of fully crystalline phase(ref.20)	130 kJ/kg
m_m , mass fraction of the matrix, (ref. 28)	0.32
K_0 , kinetic constant for melting, Eqn (5), (ref. 23)	exp (73) sec ⁻¹
E_a , activation energy for melting, Eqn (5), (ref. 23)	397 kJ/mol
E_d , activation energy for diffusion, Eqn (2),(ref.18)	1.52×10^4 (cal/mol)
k_2 , kinetic constant, Eqn (2), (ref. 18)	9.32×10^{38} sec ⁻⁴
ψ_1 , kinetic constant, Eqn (2), (ref.18)	802 °K
ψ_2 , kinetic constant, Eqn (2), (ref. 18)	1790 °K
G_o , universal constant for polymers Eqn (3), (ref.18)	75000 cm/sec
T_m^0 , equilibrium melting temperature, (refs.18)	385 °C

Recommended levels of crystallinity in carbon-fiber-reinforced-polyetheretherketone are between 25 and 35% [28]. This can be achieved by a cooling rate between 6 and 600 °C/min [28]. However, in the tape laying process, cooling rates are very high, typically above 3000 °C/min.

Figure 4 shows the temperature profiles experienced by the 20th ply during a 40-ply-lay-up process and the corresponding crystallinity development for a 0.1 m/s roller speed. Crystallization time t is defined as the time during which temperature is above the glass transition and below the melting temperature. Maximum crystallinity in the ply is less than 0.00006. Because of local heating, only the regions very close to the area exposed to the heat source are heated above the glass transition temperature. This will cause large temperature gradients, and thus high cooling rates. As shown in the figure, after three additional lay-ups, the maximum temperature in the 20th ply falls below the glass transition temperature, and hence further crystallization is not possible. Further lay-ups no longer increase crystallinity in the 20th ply.

Figure 4. Temperature profiles experienced by the top surface of the 20th ply during subsequent lay-ups and the corresponding crystallinity development for $v_x = 0.1$ m/s.

One method of increasing crystallinity is to preheat the laid-up laminate. Figure 5 shows the temperature field and the corresponding crystallinity development for 0.1 m/s roller speed when the laminate is preheated to 100 °C. Analyzed length is increased to obtain full temperature profile above the glass transition temperature. The crystallinity level, although still below the

optimum value, is significantly increased because of slower cooling rates and longer annealing times.

Figure 5. Temperature profiles and corresponding crystallinity development in the 20th ply during subsequent lay-ups for $v_x = 0.1$ m/s. Laminate is preheated to 100 °C.

When the roller velocity is reduced to 0.01 m/s, crystallinity level in the 20th ply is significantly increased, Figure 6 (a). Figure 6 (b) presents the final crystallinity levels in different plies. Little or no crystalline material forms at the top of the laminate due to shorter annealing times. Bottom of the laminate is also amorphous due to very high cooling rates caused by excessive heat loss to the steel base frame.

Figure 6 Crystallinity development in the 20th ply and final crystallinity levels in the laminate for 0.01 m/s roller speed. Laminate is preheated to 100 °C

When the preheat temperature is above the glass transition temperature, uniform crystallinity levels within the recommended range can be obtained as shown in Figure 7. Therefore, if the laminate is not preheated or preheated to low temperatures, heat treatment is needed to raise the laminate crystallinity to recommended levels.

Figure 7. Final crystallinity levels in a 40-ply laminate preheated to 150 °C. (a) $v_x = 0.1$ m/s (b) $v_x = 0.01$ m/s

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the effects of process parameters on crystallization were investigated. Reduced roller speeds resulted in increased crystallinity levels as expected. However, preheating of the laid-up laminate was found to be the major factor. Preheating the laminate above the glass transition temperature produced uniform and recommended levels of crystallinity throughout the thickness of the laminate.

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